

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 125

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 125

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 125:0 A Song of Ascents.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 125:1 שִׁיר הַמַּעֲלֹת הַבְּטָחִים</p>
<p>Psa. 125:1 Those who trust in the LORD Are as Mount Zion, which ^acannot be moved but ^babides forever.</p>	<p>בֵּית־יְהוָה כַּתֵּר-צִיּוֹן לֹא-יִזָּוֵט לְעוֹלָם יֵשֵׁב : ² יְרוּשָׁלַם הָרִים סָבִיב לָהּ וַיִּתְּנָה סָבִיב לְעַמּוֹ מִעַתָּה וְעַד- עוֹלָם : ³ כִּי לֹא יִנּוּחַ שִׁבְט הַרְשָׁע עַל גּוֹרֵל הַצְּדִיקִים לְמַעַן לֹא- יִשְׁלַחוּ הַצְּדִיקִים בְּעוֹלָתָהּ יְדֵיהֶם : ⁴ הִיטִיבָה יְהוָה לְטוֹבִים וְלִישָׁרִים בְּלִבּוֹתָם : ⁵ וְהַמַּטִּים עַקְלָקְלוֹתָם יוֹלִיכֵם יְהוָה אֶת-פְּעָלֵי הָאָוֶן שְׁלוֹם עַל-יִשְׂרָאֵל :</p>
<p>² As the mountains surround Jerusalem, So ^athe LORD surrounds His people ^bFrom this time forth and forever.</p>	
<p>³ For the ^ascepter of wickedness shall not rest upon the ¹land of the righteous, So that the righteous ^bwill not put forth their hands to do wrong.</p>	
<p>Psa. 125:4 ^aDo good, O LORD, to those who are good And to those who are ^bupright in their hearts.</p>	
<p>⁵ But as for those who ^aturn aside to their ^bcrooked ways, The LORD will lead them away with the ^cdoers of iniquity. ^dPeace be upon Israel.</p>	

References

Psalm 125:1

^aPs 46:5

^bPs 61:7; Eccl 1:4

Psalm 125:2

^aZech 2:5

^bPs 121:8

Psalm 125:3

¹Lit *lot*

^aPs 89:22; Prov 22:8; Is 14:5

^b1 Sam 24:10; Ps 55:20; Acts 12:1

Psalm 125:4

^aPs 119:68

^bPs 7:10; 11:2; 32:11; 36:10; 94:15

Psalm 125:5

^aJob 23:11; Ps 40:4; 101:3

^bProv 2:15; Is 59:8

^cPs 92:7; 94:4

^dPs 128:6; Gal 6:16

Targum

Psa. 125:1 A song that was uttered on the ascents of the abyss. The righteous who trust in the word of the LORD are like Mount Zion; it will not totter, it is inhabited forever. ² Mountains are round about Jerusalem, and the word of the LORD is round about his people from this time and forever. ³ For the scepter of wickedness will not rest on the lot of the righteous, so that the righteous will not stretch out their hand to deceit. ⁴ Be good, O LORD, to the good, and to those upright in their heart. ⁵ But those who go astray following their perversity – the LORD will make them go to Gehenna; their portion is with the workers of deceit. Peace be upon Israel!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The defense and security of the Jewish nation is a matter of primary concern. Too often in history, Israel has been vulnerable and helpless. The Psalmist emphasizes that the true fortifications of the country is internalized when the people have full faith in the LORD.

Notes on the Psalm

As other Psalmist wrote, the author of Psalm 125 reminds the people that without the LORD they are vulnerable. Indeed, people today are vulnerable when they do not have the protection of the LORD with them. It requires faith and effort to obtain the LORD's protection. Once a person has the LORD's protection, it is imperative to keep it. The simple requirement from the LORD is to follow His ways as defined in the Bible.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

